

PSYCHODIAGNOSTIC IS AN ANCIENT SCIENCE

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Annotation.

pedagogy and psychology are ancient sciences that have interested humanity for centuries. The formation period of psychodiagnostics in the 20th century. Psychodiagnostics came at the end of the 19th century and, as a science that studies individual psychological differences, sought to measure and evaluate them, and reached the beginning of the new century, having been found in debates and discussions about the dimensions of intellect.

Key words.

psychodiagnostics, psychiatrist, factor analysis, dispersion analysis, modified, intellect, empirical

Psychology is one of the ancient sciences, it appeared 2.5 thousand years ago. In the works of the ancient Greek philosophers Heraclitus, Democritus, Hippocrates, Socrates, and Plato, we can see that there are many and various opinions about the soul and spiritual life of a person. Some ideas about human spiritual life can also be found in the works of ancient Chinese and Indian thinkers. But the systematic doctrine of the human psyche was first created by the Greek philosopher Aristotle (Arastu). In his work "About the soul", he spoke in detail about the psyche and tried to explain many aspects of it. At the same time, he gave a historical commentary on the opinions of his predecessors. For this reason, he was considered the "father" of psychology. In ancient times, doctors and other researchers assumed that mental phenomena are the activity of the brain, and correctly understood various mental illnesses as disorders of the brain. No mental process can be formed by itself, the psyche arises only due to the influence of one or another stimulus on the brain. The beginning of the psyche is the effect of the stimulus, and its result is the response of the organism to the stimulus. Any mental activity consists only of the reflective activity of the brain. Clinical period of psychological knowledge. The ideas that the psyche is a product of the brain and nervous system can be connected with the history of modern psychodiagnostics,

the clinical period of the formation of psychological knowledge in the quarter and a half of the 19th century. This period was characterized by the fact that important tasks in the collection and analysis of empirical and psychological knowledge about a person were carried out with the help of doctors. He was interested in doctors because of the mental and nervous diseases that are spreading in the developing countries of the world.

Psychiatrists continuously monitored patients in European hospitals and recorded their results and conclusions. At the same time, methods of psychodiagnostics, such as observation, survey, document analysis, were being formed. The development of psychodiagnostics at this time had a free nature, and such a situation was inextricably linked with the quantitative nature of psychodiagnostic methods.

The role of V. Wund's laboratory in the formation of psychodiagnostics. The creation of quantitative methods of psychodiagnostics is based on the first experimental psychological laboratory created in the second half of the 19th century under the leadership of the German psychologist V. Wund.

In this laboratory, they used various equipment for psychodiagnostic purposes. Also, in this period, the creation of the psychophysical law, which explained the existence of quantitative connections between mental and physical states, accelerated the creation of methods of quantitative psychodiagnostics. A basic psychophysical law opened up the possibility of measuring psychological states, and this innovation led to the creation of a subjective scale for measuring intuition. In accordance with this law, the main object of measurement was the human senses, and for a long time, until the end of the 19th century, practical psychodiagnostics was limited to the measurement of sensory processes. Modern methods of psychodiagnostics related to the study of psychological processes, characteristics and conditions of a person began to appear at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. Now, with the help of qualified psychologists, some areas of probability theory and mathematical statistics, on which quantitative psychodiagnostic methods are based, are rapidly developing. However, now mathematical statistics are used not only in psychology, but also in other sciences such as biology and economics. After a certain time, special methods for quantitative psychodiagnosis of psychological conditions were created. For example, factor analysis is one of them, which was first used in psychodiagnostics of personality traits and mental development. The first statistically based tests. The first special, psychometric research center was established in England by the famous English psychologist Galton. In 1884, he founded the Anthropometric

Laboratory. One of the tasks of the laboratory was to collect statistical data about human abilities. Visitors to this laboratory had the opportunity to voluntarily measure their abilities, and almost 10,000 people used it in its time. Galton was the organizer of the application of statistics in psychology and made significant contributions to the development of statistical methods. In 1877, Galton proposed the use of the correlation method in psychology, and for this he called for the cooperation of mathematical scientists such as Fisher and Pearson. Together, scientists achieve successful results not only in the field of mathematics, but also in psychology. For example, Fisher discovered dispersion analysis, and another mathematician, Galton's contemporary Spearman, discovered factor analysis. Spearman took a special place in the history of psychology with the article "General intellect, objectively defined and defined" published in 1904. One of the first statistically based tests related to intelligence was developed and published by the French scientist A. Binet in 1905-1907. After some time, he perfected this test in collaboration with another French scientist T. Simon, and it entered the history of psychodiagnostics as the Bine-Simon test.

In the second half of the 20s of the 20th century, new psychological, including intellectual and personality tests, which perform psychodiagnostics of various processes and characteristics, began to appear. Among the latest quantitative psychodiagnostic methods, sociometric tests related to socio-psychological research also took place.

The formation period of psychodiagnostics in the 20th century. Psychodiagnostics arrived at the end of the 19th century and, as a science that studies individual psychological differences, sought to measure and evaluate them. traveled the distance to the tests.

Historically, such a situation has arisen that from the time of its origin and the end of the 19th century, psychodiagnostics was intended to measure individual coincidences in intellectual fields, and if we remember what expectations were placed on the human mind in the passing 19th century, we will see that this is not a coincidence. Ahead, discussions and discoveries of new successes and failures, which determined the development of psychodiagnostics in the 20th century, awaited. As mentioned above, it was A. Bine's tests that had many significant results in determining individual differences at the beginning of the 20th century. The first crisis test of intelligence is related to its name. The Bine scale has been widely used in various countries. Among the first, this test was used by Henry Goddard in the USA. He included it in the group of methods for checking immigrants from Europe. As demonstrated by Goddard's work, this non-adaptive

test screened subjects with poor or no English proficiency. As a result of this examination, 83% of Jews, 80% of Hungarians, 79% of Italians, and 87% of Russians could be characterized as mentally retarded. G. Goddard's unsatisfactory translation of the Bine-Simon scale (edited in 1908), another American psychologist Lewis Madison Termen and H. D. Childs jointly modified this test in a new version. His approach was to test the scale for validity and reliability tasks, as Binet had done, but this time in the United States. Many tasks of the test have been modified and new ones have been added. This scale (the Stanford version of the Bine-Simon scale) was standardized on 2100 children and 180 adults. It covers the age range from three to older, but there is no test for 11-year-olds. The results are based on the age-matched mental development and can be expressed in the form of an IQ or IQ based on the location of the IQ using this scale, Thermen proposed the following classification scheme: IQ 90 - 109 means average mental ability shows that an IQ below 70 indicates mental retardation, an IQ above 140 indicates genius. In doing so, he noted that the objections to the determinations by which they were made were willingly placed, and that the classification chart itself was intended to be used as a general guide to measure the new dimensions. Another merit of Termin is that, for the first time in history, a number of guidelines have been developed for conducting the test and determining the results. Therman has repeatedly noted that deviations from standard test procedures can lead to serious errors.

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